

Enhancing the Investigation of Environmental Crimes Based on Multiple Data Sources

Freddy Rivas Gonzalez¹[0000-0002-2392-5466], Marco Piras², Mihaela Violeta Gheorghe³, George Boldeanu³[0000-0001-7627-5359], Joao Gama⁴, Matias Molina⁴, Ray Harris⁵, and Ray Purdi⁵

¹ GMV-EST frivas@gmv.com

² Politecnico di Torino marco.piras@polito.it

³ GMV-RO george.boldeanu@gmv.com, mgheorghe@gmv.com

⁴ INESC TEC joao.gama@inesctec.pt, matias.d.molina@inesctec.pt

⁵ Air & Evidence rh@space-evidence.net, info@space-evidence.net

Abstract. The EMERITUS project, funded by the EC Horizon Europe programme, contribute to combat waste crimes using advanced data sources and EU space program resources. These crimes, such as waste dumping and trafficking of hazardous waste, harm climate, health, and biodiversity but remain profitable due to low detection risks and penalties. EMERITUS supports law enforcement with an evidence-based intelligence platform, utilizing satellite imagery, ML/DL based models, and time series analysis to detect illegal activities such as new landfills. It leverages open datasets from the ESA Copernicus program for cost-effective monitoring, addressing limitations with machine learning and integrating UAVs and in-situ sensors. The project combines open-source satellite resources with other technologies to enhance investigations, providing a comprehensive tool for detecting and combating environmental crimes, ultimately improving law enforcement efforts.

Keywords: Copernicus Program · Machine Learning · UAV · Satellite Imagery · Open data · Deep Learning · Sentinel-2

1 Introduction

Environmental crime, especially waste-related activities, threatens the EU's environment, public health, and economy. It includes illegal waste trafficking, dumping, and water pollution, requiring a coordinated response due to its complexity and high profitability, with an estimated annual value of €70-213 billion [1], being the illegal waste disposal and trafficking a significant contributors to this figure with €11 billion per year⁶. The new Environmental Crime Directive [2] is a key step in the EU's fight against serious environmental offences, with projects like EMERITUS providing technological solutions to support Law Enforcement Authorities (LEAs) and Border Guards (BGs). The EMERITUS

⁶ <https://baselgovernance.org/news/illegal-waste-trade-whats-driving-multi-billion-dollar-transnational-crime-and-what-could-stop>

platform integrates AI-based analytic components to detect waste disposal sites and uses change detection techniques for locating landfills. It combines developments from project participants and external providers (e.g. other EU funded projects), utilizing remote sensing images (e.g., Sentinel-2) and UAV, employing AI and conventional imagery analysis methods.

The main goal of this paper is to show how individual components developed under geomatics principles, such as the collection, storage, processing, analysis, and presentation of spatially referenced data [3], integrated in a single-entry platform support efficiently the investigation of waste-related environmental crime.

2 EMERITUS workflow

The EMERITUS platform workflow involves the development and integration of multiple components, each tailored to meet specific needs and requirements identified during the initial phases of the project through extensive interactions. To ensure results are practical and effective, under the EMERITUS context, four relevant use cases (UC) were selected to guide and validate the developments with real data. Each UC use different approaches to cover particular needs defined in the EMERITUS proposal phase. This paper explores the developments

Fig. 1. EMERITUS workflow.

of three UCs. UC2 focuses on developing a component that leverages cameras mounted on UAVs and satellites. The data captured by these cameras is analysed using AI models to extract valuable insights. Meanwhile, UC3 develops another component that utilizes data from S2 satellites, also analysed with DL using custom architectures to enhance the efficiency identifying potential waste disposal sites. Additionally, a separate component, associated to UC3, is developed using AI for change detection, enabling the identification of significant alterations over time, leveraged in the analysis of imagery using Google Satellite API services to acquire data. UC4, on the other hand, employs a combination of conventional methodology and DL based on time series analysis to develop

its solution to identify landfills. This approach provides a robust framework for understanding temporal pattern to monitor landfills. Once these individual components are developed, they are integrated into the EMERITUS platform. All components offer solutions aimed at supporting the investigation of environmental crimes, thereby enhancing the platform's overall capability. From a general perspective, the workflow to provide a suitable solution to the end user consider as a co-creation phase, involving the LEAs and BGs to collect needs and define requirements, a development phase, including an individual testing sub-phase, and the integration phase where all possibilities for connecting the individual components to the EMERITUS platform are explored. (Fig. 1).

3 EMERITUS Platform

The EMERITUS platform is robust, scalable, and portable, optimized for heterogeneous cloud environments with special routines for integrating various systems (Fig. 2). It features a precise software stack and development method, ideal for

Fig. 2. A schematic overview of the EMERITUS Processing System.

adapting to project use cases. To drive the processing, storage, and access requirements for the EMERITUS project in a best scalable, reliable, and portable way, a domain-driven-design (DDD) approach for the setup of the asked environment was chosen. This means that all components of the system are mapped into a well-defined microservice architecture and take advantage of state-of-the-art open-technologies regarding data storage, data-access, process scheduling and monitoring components. Led horizontally, in terms of computational power, and vertically, in terms of storage volume and complexity. The data-products in the EMERITUS system are logically stored in such a way, that further processing and accessibility by means of different data-representation paradigms (structured or non-structured) are easily possible in a technological sense. In addition to a comprehensive User Interface to present data in an easy-to-understand manner,

the system can serve data-warehouse environments and their reporting needs by means of data connectors to a central result database with geoinformation extensions.

The design of the system is optimized for large and heterogenous data-driven workflows and most flexible regarding data-storage and access. The system is best suited for georeferenced data, such as Earth Observation imagery, Drone, ancillary (e.g., sensors) as well as in-situ data sources and their derived products.

4 EMERITUS Components

4.1 Very High-Resolution Imagery in the detection and classification of waste (EMERITUS UC2)

UC2 monitors industrial storage centers, aiding LEAs in complex investigations. It explores using drones for enhanced data collection and processing, providing specialized tools for efficient evidence gathering and monitoring of waste-related crimes [4].

1. The objectives of UC2 are identifying and standardizing geospatial and informative data crucial for local operators engaged in waste crime investigations.
2. Defining simulation scenarios for data acquisition, analysis, testing, training, and validation purposes.
3. Implementing automatic and semi-automatic classification of Very High Resolution (VHR) satellite and drone datasets, leveraging Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies [5]. Additionally, Research and Development (R&D) activities focus on fine-tuning these tools and utilizing the GALILEO satellite constellation for accurate positioning [6].

The UC2 initiative has been tested in two distinct scenarios: a semi-controlled site in Monte Calvarina (Verona, Italy) and an active quarry in Torino (Italy). Within these sites, various technologies have been evaluated (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. UC2 sites: Calvarina site (left) - Active quarry (right)

Multicopter drones have been deployed to collect images using different digital cameras (RGB, multispectral, thermal) to generate 3D models via photogram-

metry, estimate volume changes, and classify different water types [7]. Furthermore, aerial LiDAR technology mounted on UAVs has been utilized to obtain point clouds for classification and volume change detection [8]. Terrestrial LiDAR technologies have also been implemented for point cloud collection through both static and dynamic approaches, including the adoption of SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) solutions [9].

The methodologies employed in this research enable a multi-temporal monitoring approach, allowing for the observation of site evolution over time using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) solutions [10]. This capability will be integrated into the EMERITUS platform. In the scope of UC2, five different waste types have been analyzed, including tires, sand, barrels, batteries, and plastics. As a result, thematic maps can be created for waste type identification, 3D models can be generated to extract geometric information (such as volumes and sizes), and comparisons can be made across various time epochs [11].

4.2 AI techniques applied to EO for detection of waste disposal sites (EMERITUS UC3)

Earth Observation (EO) has evolved into a big data analytics challenge. To meet the growing demand for advanced environmental monitoring, organizations have liberalized access to satellite imagery through programs like Copernicus and developed cloud infrastructures such as Google Earth Engine. Deep Learning (DL) has become essential, leveraging accessible computing power and vast data collections. By 2023, DL models predominantly rely on very high-resolution (VHR) EO data, with fewer benchmarks utilizing multispectral data. [12]. Free data like S2, with its wide availability and high temporal resolution, is crucial for preventing waste-related environmental crimes in Romania. Deep Learning (DL) applications leveraging multispectral imagery are essential. A custom training dataset was created using VHR imagery and multispectral sensors to identify waste sites, addressing challenges of small size and spectral mixing. This approach involved initially identifying larger, more conspicuous waste sites and utilizing these sites to train a classification model. Subsequently, this trained model was applied to detect smaller, more challenging waste sites, leveraging the knowledge gained from the analysis of larger sites. This hierarchical methodology proved effective in overcoming the limitations imposed by the size and spectral complexity of illegal waste sites. To choose the best DL model, we used Optuna [13], a hyperparameter optimization framework. The best results were from DeepLabV3+ and ResNeSt101e [14]. To handle imbalanced data, Tversky Focal Loss was used, with optimal parameters: alpha 0.3, beta 0.7, and gamma 1.45. This combination helped maximize true identifications, and the gamma value of 1.45 allowed the model to have a balance between the more difficult examples and simpler ones. In Table 1 different configurations are presented that were results of the Optuna hyperparameter tuning with the final version that consisted of a DeepLabV3+ and ResNeSt101e encoder that was trained for 400 epochs and 6 bands to achieve a test IOU of 0.61.

Table 1. Optuna hyperparameter results.

Model + Encoder vIOU	S2 bands tPrecision	vPrecision tRecall	vRecall tIOU
DeepLabV3 + & ResNeSt 101e 0.63	02, 03, 04, 08, 11, 12 0.67	0.70 0.86	0.85 0.61
DeepLabV3+ & ResNeSt 200e 0.62	02, 03, 04, 08, 11, 12 0.59	0.75 0.76	0.78 0.50
DeepLabV3+ & SeResNeXt 101 32x4d 0.57	02, 03, 04, 08, 11, 12 0.86	0.8 0.43	0.67 0.40
Manet & SeResNeXt 101 32x4d 0.55	02, 03, 04, 08, 11, 12 0.64	0.77 0.69	0.67 0.49
DeepLabV3+ & ResNeSt 101e 0.59	02, 03, 04, 05, 8A, 12 0.67	0.75 0.65	0.73 0.49

At inference, the T35TPN tile was chosen for its environmental similarity to Romania. From 2018 to 2023, 47 potential illegal waste sites were identified, increasing from 23 in 2018 to 47 in 2023. Validation with Moldovan authorities is ongoing.

4.3 Overcoming challenges in illegal landfill waste detection from a second approach applied to UC3

This section details our efforts in monitoring illegal waste disposal. We encountered challenges due to limited data and the high costs of high-resolution imagery. To overcome these, we focused on AI and deep learning models, despite the scarcity of labeled data and reliance on low-resolution images. A major technical challenge is the discrepancy between the high-resolution imagery needed for object detection models and the lower-resolution imagery available from open data sources, like S2. One first question is if it is possible to leverage high-resolution literature datasets for building models that could be queried with lower resolutions. Our research revealed a significant drop in detection performance as image resolution decreased. The AI models trained on very high-resolution (VHR) datasets struggled when applied to lower-resolution imagery. To mitigate this issue, we explored super-resolution techniques to enhance lower-quality images, making them more comparable to the high-resolution images used for training. Although super-resolution preprocessing provided improvements in the overall performance, it also introduced sensitivity issues in the model, requiring careful adjustment of classification thresholds [15] We developed AI methods to address different tasks related to waste detection. Our primary focus was on two key tasks: Image classification and Image Segmentation. Fig. 4 shows examples of both methodologies.

We developed deep learning models to classify high-resolution images and detect illegal landfill sites using data from literature and newly collected data from Portugal, in collaboration with the public agency of territory monitoring and Google Satellite API service [15], [16].The model identifies illegal landfill

Fig. 4. Examples of waste classification (left) and waste segmentation (right). The classification shows a heatmap as output indicating the most likely region to be waste. The segmentation sample shows the ground truth in red and the predicted segment in yellow.

waste and its likely region within the image. We addressed segmentation tasks with limited annotations by combining classification models, explainability, and unsupervised segmentation methods [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22]. Our findings show that while open data sources like S2 are cost-effective, they pose challenges due to lower resolutions. Combining AI models with super-resolution techniques helps, but adapting high-resolution models to low-resolution domains remains difficult. For few-shot segmentation, we introduced new evaluation metrics and optimized models using feature engineering to understand waste-related visual patterns, aiming to continuously improve EMERITUS technology.

4.4 Time series applied in the detection of landfills (EMERITUS UC4)

Data from the S2 satellites offer the opportunity to use time series of Earth observation data to monitor the surface of the Earth. Given the presence of cloud cover then these optical wavelength satellites produce far fewer images, but they still do produce a considerable amount of data. One attraction is that the data from the two satellites are open data and are free of charge. We used time series of S2 data in two models to detect potential landfill sites. The instrument carried on S2 satellites collects data in 13 spectral bands in the visible, near infrared and short-wave infrared wavebands. Four bands have a 10 metres pixel size, six bands are at 20 metres and three bands are at 60 metres spatial resolution. The S2 data we used were downloaded from the Copernicus Open Access Hub⁷ The

⁷ <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/#/home>

processing level chosen for use in the work presented in this paper is L2A which is bottom of the atmosphere reflectance produced by the ESA SenCor processor⁸. The two detection models we used work best with several dates of S2 data, that is time series of Earth observation data. Data from several years and from different seasons were used, depending on the availability of cloud free data. This creates a data cube for any one target area: the data cube typically consists of between 10 and 100 dates of data for a S2 tile which is an area on the ground of 100 x 100km. In the first model, S2 data in the visible, near infrared and short-wave infrared parts of the electromagnetic spectrum are used separately and also used in combination. Indices such as the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and the Normalised Short Wave Vegetation Index (NSW) are calculated for each pixel. Having calculated initial indices, the data are then analysed using change detection plus the elimination of standard land cover types such building footprints, roadways, trees and water features.

Fig. 5. Detection model for the Athens region. White dots are the results of the sites detected by the first detection model and the yellow dots are the sites detected by the second model.

There are several open access data bases of land cover available to enable this filtering including OpenStreetMap, Corine, ESA WorldCover map and the S2 10m global land cover map. In the second model, we used a deep learning approach. The model is composed of an auto-encoded feature extraction network (often referred to as the "backbone") and a classification head. The input imagery is passed through multiple stages of convolutions and down-sampling operations in the encoder part of the network. The decoder portion then uses the lower-dimensional encoding of the input imagery ("latent space") to recreate as accurate a representation of the input imagery as possible. The sites of potential landfill are then extracted based on the training data. The result of each multi-temporal

⁸ <https://step.esa.int/main/snap-supported-plugins/sen2cor/>

detection model is a list of latitude and longitude locations of potential waste or landfill sites. An example of the detection model output is shown in Fig. 5.

5 Conclusions

The EMERITUS platform is a scalable, portable system optimized for cloud environments, using a domain-driven design and microservice architecture for reliable processing, storage, and access. It integrates various components and technologies, making it adaptable to different use cases, with a comprehensive user interface and data connectors enhancing usability and reporting. EMERITUS UC2 focuses on monitoring industrial storage centers using high-resolution imagery, aiding LEAs in investigations and inspections. Objectives include standardizing geospatial data, defining simulation scenarios, and using the platform for automatic classification of satellite and UAV-acquired data. R&D activities leverage the GALILEO constellation for robust positioning, enhancing waste crime investigations. EMERITUS UC3 uses AI and Earth Observation (EO) data to detect waste disposal sites, addressing challenges of identifying small, heterogeneous sites with high-resolution imagery and deep learning models. Techniques like Optuna for hyperparameter optimization and Tversky Focal Loss for imbalanced datasets improve detection accuracy. EMERITUS UC4 utilizes time series data from S2 satellites to detect potential landfill sites, employing multispectral imaging and indices like NDVI for change detection. This approach enhances landfill detection accuracy despite challenges like cloud cover, supporting environmental monitoring and waste crime prevention. These efforts support law enforcement and open new research avenues to improve the platform's capabilities.

Acknowledgments. This paper is the results of contributions of partners involved in EMERITUS project. EMERITUS have received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101073874.

References

1. Environmental Crime. EUROPOL: <https://www.europol.europa.eu/crime-areas/environmental-crime> (2022)
2. Environmental Crime Directive. Retrieved from European Commission: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/law-and-governance/environmental-compliance-assurance/environmental-crime-directive_en (2024)
3. Gomasasca, Mario A. (2010). Basics of geomatics. *Applied Geomatics*, 137-136. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12518-010-0029-6>
4. Pompili, M., De Rosa, R., & Santoro, F. (2020). Drones and Remote Sensing Technologies for Environmental Monitoring. *Sensors*, 20(12), 3421.
5. Balzani, P., Albrecht, J., & Rizzo, G. (2021). Application of Machine Learning for Waste Classification in Aerial Images. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 294, 112911.

6. Fischer, M., Giergiel, G., & Ozdemir, H. (2019). Enhancing GNSS Data with GALILEO for Environmental Monitoring. *GPS Solutions*, 23(1), 15.
7. Meyer, T., Peterson, A., & Loughead, T. (2022). Drones in Waste Monitoring: Advances and Applications. *Remote Sensing*, 14(2), 150.
8. Sliusar, I., Sliusar, V., & Sereda, V. (2022). Aerial LiDAR for Volume Change Detection in Mining Areas. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 11(3), 123.
9. Hamid Taheri & Zhao Chun Xia. (2021). SLAM; definition and evolution. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2020.10403>
10. Kumar, S., Singh, R., & Kaur, A. (2021). Geographic Information Systems in Environmental Monitoring: Trends and Applications. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 193, 784.
11. Cheng, Z., Wang, P., & Zhao, Y. (2021). Utilizing Multispectral Imaging for Waste Identification in Landfills: A GIS Approach. *Waste Management*, 130, 179-190.
12. Ivica, Dimitrovski; Kitanovski, Ivan; Kocev, Dragi. (2023). Current Trends in Deep Learning for Earth Observation: An Open-Source Benchmark Arena for Image Classification. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 197, 18-35. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*. doi:doi: 10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2023.01.014
13. Akiba, Takuya; Sano, Shotaro; Yanase, Toshihiko; Ohta, Takeru; Koyama, Masanori. (2019). Optuna: A Next-Generation Hyperparameter Optimization Framework. doi:doi: 10.48550/arXiv
14. Chen, L-C; Zhu, Y.; Papandreou, G.; Schroff, F.; Adam, H. (2018). Encoder-Decoder with Atrous Separable Convolution for Semantic Image Segmentation. *Art. no. arXiv:1802.02611*. doi:doi:10.48550/arXiv.1802.02611
15. Molina, M.; Ribeiro, R. P.; Veloso, B.; Gama, J. (2018, 04). Super-Resolution Analysis for Landfill Waste Classification. *International Symposium on Intelligent Data Analysis*, 155 - 166. (S. N. Switzerland, Ed.)
16. Torres, R.N.; Fraternali, P. (2023). AerialWaste dataset for landfill discovery in aerial and satellite images. 10, 63. *Sci Data*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-01976-9>
17. Ronneberger, O.; Fischer, P.; Brox, T. (2015). U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation. 18th international conference. part III 18, pp. 234 - 241. Munich - Germany: Springer International Publishing.
18. He, K.; Gkioxari, G.; Dollar, P.; Girshick, R. (2017). Mask r-cnn. *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, (pp. 2961-2969).
19. Kirillov, A.; Mintun, E.; Ravi, N.; Mao, H.; Rolland, C.; Gustafson, L.; Girshick, R. (2013). Segment anything. *IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, (pp. 4015-4026).
20. Zhou, B.; Khosla, A.; Lapedriza, A.; Oliva, A.; & Torralba, A. (2016). Learning deep features for discriminative localization. *IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, (pp. 2921-2929).
21. Gunning, D.; Stefik, M.; Choi, J.; Miller, T.; Stumpf, S.; & Yang, G. Z. (2019). XAI-Explainable artificial intelligence. 4, p. 37. *Science robotics*.
22. Ribeiro, M. T.; Singh, S.; & Guestrin, C. (2016). Why should i trust you? Explaining the predictions of any classifier. 22nd ACM SIGKDD international conference on knowledge discovery and data mining, (pp. 1135-1144).